

**ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ ПРАВ ЧЕЛОВЕКА, ТЕНДЕНЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРАВ
ЧЕЛОВЕКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ, ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ И
МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ГАРАНТИЙ ПРАВ ЧЕЛОВЕКА**

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Abstract: В статье описывается системная работа, проводимая в области прав человека в нашей стране сегодня, место прав человека в национальной правовой системе, важные направления государственной политики по обеспечению прав человека на сегодняшний день, образовательная программа по правам человека, права, его предполагаемые задачи и содержание.

Keywords: права человека, международные документы по правам человека, механизмы обеспечения соблюдения прав человека, категория прав человека, государственная политика в области прав человека, национальная стратегия, образование в области прав человека.

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**HUMAN RIGHTS EDUCATION, HUMAN RIGHTS DEVELOPMENT
TENDENCIES IN UZBEKISTAN, PRIORITY DIRECTIONS AND
MECHANISMS OF PROVIDING HUMAN RIGHTS GUARANTEES**

Abstract: The article describes the systematic work carried out in the field of human rights in our country today, the place of human rights in the national legal system, the important directions of the state policy on ensuring human rights today, the educational program on human rights, its prospective tasks and content.

Keywords: Human rights, International documents on human rights, Human rights enforcement mechanisms, Human rights category, State policy in the field of human rights, National strategy, Education in the field of human rights.

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**EDUCACIÓN EN DERECHOS HUMANOS, TENDENCIAS DE DESARROLLO
DE DERECHOS HUMANOS EN UZBEKISTÁN, DIRECCIONES
PRIORITARIAS Y MECANISMOS PARA ASEGURAR LAS GARANTÍAS DE
DERECHOS HUMANOS**

Abstract: El artículo describe el trabajo sistemático realizado en el campo de los derechos humanos en nuestro país en la actualidad, el lugar de los derechos humanos en el ordenamiento jurídico nacional, áreas importantes de la política estatal para garantizar los derechos humanos en la actualidad, y el programa educativo en derechos humanos, derechos, sus funciones previstas y su contenido

Keywords: derechos humanos, instrumentos internacionales de derechos humanos, mecanismos de exigibilidad de derechos humanos, categoría de derechos humanos, política pública de derechos humanos, estrategia nacional, educación en derechos humanos.

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"Human Rights" In general, the concept is comprehensive and essentially a broad concept. While talking about human rights, first of all, each of us should understand the place of a person in social life. Centuries have passed and the concept of human rights has not lost its original essence. On the contrary, it has been refined over the years and is embodied in social life as a concept that creates the foundation of opportunities and guarantees for people. Human rights represent the possibilities of a person in social life, defined by laws. These rights and freedoms give a person the opportunity to develop his human qualities, mental abilities, use them, and satisfy his natural and other needs. Human rights, which have universal value, constitute the conceptual basis of the activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in all spheres of social, political, economic and spiritual life. As a full-fledged member of the world community, the Republic of Uzbekistan implicitly recognizes the priority of human rights and considers the protection and promotion of human rights as its strategic important task 5 .

The concept of "human rights" has a special place in today's social life, which is related to the gradual improvement and wide-scale implementation of human rights In this regard, Professor A.Kh. Saidov says the following in his opinion, - the term "generally recognized human rights" reflects the importance of international documents no less than the term "international standards" because they are developed at the interstate level and are intended to regulate interstate cooperation. In fact, human rights determine the normal activities of people in society, which are universally recognized and mandatory for all countries. In any advanced democratic country, human rights are considered as a supreme value. Shows how promising the chosen path of our growing country is. It is considered one of the most important conditions for increasing legal awareness and legal culture in society, ensuring the rule of law and strengthening legitimacy. In recent years, significant work has been done on the fundamental reform of our national legal system, the formation of legal culture in society, and the training of qualified legal personnel, there are still a number of problems and shortcomings that prevent the formation of respect for human rights and freedoms, raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, and increasing the level of legal literacy of citizens in the society 8 . In the field of forming the legal culture of the population, especially in the field of human rights, it is necessary to form the initial skills in this field for each person . For this, the role of education, more specifically, the role of education in the field of human rights deserves special attention. Many international agreements oblige the state to inform the population about the contents of these agreements. For example, Article 42 of the -Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted by the UN, states: " Participating -States shall, using

appropriate and effective means, undertake to inform both adults and children widely about the principles and provisions of the Convention "3. Human rights education with international norms determines the obligations of states arising from international agreements in the field of human rights, and by fulfilling these obligations, states form the understanding and skills of human rights and the culture of human rights in the minds of citizens. Human rights education is considered a component of citizens' legal education, and is of particular importance in the current conditions, when the process of liberalization and democratization is underway in all spheres of social life, the rule of law is being built, and a just civil society is being formed. 4

It is necessary to form new values and skills in respect of human rights and freedoms in the population and ultimately to form a culture aimed at developing respect for and observance of human rights at the national level. People's knowledge of their rights and freedoms should be a prerequisite for the implementation of the constitutional guarantee of individual rights. Education in the field of human rights is of great importance in encouraging everyone's respect for human rights and ensuring their comprehensive observance . awareness of one's rights and freedoms serves to raise the culture of human rights, which implies compliance with one's obligations. In our country, targeted work is being carried out to ensure human rights and freedoms, a whole system of legal documents has been developed, and national institutions for the protection of human rights and freedoms are working successfully. On December 10, 2004, the UN General Assembly adopted the "World Education Program" in the field of human rights in order to support the implementation of educational programs in the field of human rights. This educational program has 4 stages:

Phase 1 covered human rights education in secondary education institutions in 2005-2009.

The 2nd stage, in 2010-2014 was devoted to the education of teachers-coaches and civil servants in the field of human rights in higher education institutions.

The 3rd stage, in 2015-2019, media representatives were trained in the field of human rights.

In the 4th stage, in 2020-2024, expanding the rights and opportunities of young people through education in the field of human rights is defined as a priority task. To date, the 1-2-3 stages of this educational program have been implemented with positive results, and the 4th stage has been successfully implemented. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan has joined more than 80 international documents on human rights, including 6 main treaties and 4 optional protocols of the United Nations. He regularly presents national reports to the UN Human Rights Council and treaty committees .

The tense political situation in the world today shows how important the issue of human rights protection is. It is a well-known fact that human rights occupy the leading place in the human society at present. The role of the issue of human rights in the construction of any humane and just civil society is incomparable. The main condition for the construction of a democratic, legal state is the universal recognition and protection of basic rights and freedoms, as well as the creation of an effective mechanism for guaranteeing the rights of every person in society. Human rights determine the fullness of life on earth and serve as an integral part of the cultures of nations, the highest manifestation of the moral and legal rights of humanity. That is why universally recognized human rights occupy one of the most important places among the spiritual values of the modern world. He strengthened the legal basis of the mutual responsibility of the individual and the state of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The priority in the "Man - State" relationship belongs to the man. The activities of state authorities should be focused on the protection of human rights and freedoms.

Human rights are the core of humane democratic legal consciousness. The level of legal consciousness is not only awareness of rights and knowledge of laws. This is, first of all, compliance with laws and readiness to fulfill them, obedience to the law, respect for law and justice. Perfect legal documents are an important condition for raising legal culture, a necessary sign of the establishment of a legal state. It is necessary to consistently coordinate the legislation of our country with international norms and standards in the field of human rights. Laws must be vital, inextricably linked with practice and derived from it. In this case, laws should have direct effect. Executive bodies can adopt by-laws not as additions to laws, but only to ensure their implementation. 6

Human rights, enshrined in the UN Charter and international conventions, as well as in the constitutions of various countries of the world, are being absorbed into our consciousness as basic and inseparable rights. The list and content of the basic rights and freedoms of a human being is confirmed in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and a number of normative documents, and the rights and freedoms confirmed in the declaration can be divided into four categories.

- The first group is personal rights and freedoms
- The second group is political rights and freedoms
- The third group includes socio-economic rights and freedoms
- The fourth group includes cultural rights and freedoms .

In the category of human rights, the place of personal rights and freedoms is of great importance. In this place, personal rights ensure the freedom of a person in his life and protect him from illegal interference . The personal rights and freedoms

enshrined in Chapter 7 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan fully correspond to the norms of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

We can include the following in such rights:

The right to life, (Article 24 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to freedom and personal integrity (Article 25 of the Uz.Res.Cons.)

Presumption of innocence (Article 26 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Freedom of belief, (Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to move from one place to another (Article 28 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to privacy (Article 27 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

At this point, if we talk about the political rights of citizens, they are usually the rights that belong only to the citizens of a certain state and are related to the management of state and community affairs in the political life of the state. In our current constitution, the system of political rights

The right to vote and be elected (Article 117 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to hold meetings, demonstrations, rallies (Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Joining various associations and political parties (Article 34 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to directly and indirectly participate in the management of state affairs (Article 32 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Rights and other rights (Article 29 of Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan) are included.

Social, economic and cultural rights are, by their nature, the right to certain material and spiritual benefits. In satisfying the economic, social and cultural needs of a person, his rights are in the main place. then securing the property and economic rights of our people was considered as one of the priority directions of the state policy. As an absolute solution for this, our General Assembly has a special place among the adopted normative legal documents.

The right to work (Article 37 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to receive social security (Article 39 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Private property right, (Article 36 of Uz.Res.Cons.)

The right to unemployment protection (Article 37 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

The right to rest, (Article 38 of Uz.Res.Cons)

The right to education, (Article 40 of Uz.Res.Cons.)

The right to use medical services (Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan)

Use of cultural achievements right (Article 42 of Uz.Res.Cons.)

Freedom of scientific and technical creativity (Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

"Individual-society-state" reflects the essence of the reforms implemented in our country today. Therefore, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh .M . Mirziyoyev The fact that "the principle of rule of law established in our constitution is an important guarantee of ensuring human rights and freedoms in our society and effective implementation of all reforms" is a special proof that a real mechanism of ensuring human rights is being established in our country.

At this point, when it comes to human rights, it is necessary to pay special attention to the role of the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" , "more than 90 national constitutions adopted after 1948 reflect the provisions of the declaration and (or) these provisions were included under its influence" 6 . As noted above, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights later paved the way for the adoption of other human rights agreements.

Including

1. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women; Convention on the Rights of the Child; Convention against Torture and Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading -Treatment or Punishment ; International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination: Migrant Workers -and Their the International Convention on the Protection of Family Members; the Convention on the Rights of the Disabled and other normative documents.

As sources of universally recognized human rights in the Islamic system: Universal Declaration of Human Rights; Cairo Declaration of Human Rights in Islam; Arab Charter of Human Rights. Can add the following to the sources of the European system of universally recognized human rights: European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms; European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading -Treatment or Punishment; European Social Charter. Among these agreements, the central place is occupied by international covenants on human rights.

Implementation of effective cooperation with the Public Chamber under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and civil society institutions in the field of

fulfilling the international obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan on human rights is defined as a priority task. The issue of ensuring human rights and freedoms in our country is becoming the main criterion of democratic reforms aimed at creating comfortable and decent living conditions for our people.

International standards on human rights are being systematically and gradually implemented into national legislation and law enforcement practice program was accepted. The National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights was adopted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 22, 2020. In order to ensure the implementation of the national strategy, it was decided to introduce training courses on human rights for higher educational institutions.

At this point, let's talk about the tasks of the National Strategy.

The priority tasks of the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are:

1) improvement of the legislation taking into account the priorities of the socio-economic development of the country, generally recognized international standards and the obligations of Uzbekistan in the field of human rights, as well as the recommendations of the statutory bodies and treaty committees of the UN;

2) to increase the role of parliament and civil society institutions in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals of Uzbekistan in the period up to 2030, to strengthen the rule of law, to harmonize national legislation and law enforcement with international obligations on human rights;

3) International ratings and indices in the field of human rights and freedoms of Uzbekistan (rule of law, quality of rule-making, effectiveness of government activity, freedom of speech and information, fight against crime and corruption, conditions for doing business, global competitiveness, innovative development, etc.) ensure that it is among the 50 leading countries in the world ;

4) in order to eliminate human rights violations, ensure the independence of the judiciary, improve the activities of prosecutor's offices and strengthen the powers of the justice system, as well as create broad conditions for the activities of national institutions for the protection of human rights, the national system of monitoring and evaluating the state policy in the field of human rights. further development, raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, forming the culture of human rights in the society;

5) to increase the efficiency of openness and mutual cooperation of the activities of state authorities and management bodies, civil society institutions, mass media and the private sector in the protection of personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights, as well as the practice of holding consultations with civil society institutions in the process of law-making improvement;

6) preventing and combating crime, especially human trafficking, corruption, torture, organized and transnational crime, as well as ensuring the observance of justice and human rights in the system of places of detention of detainees, prisoners and convicts;

7) to ensure the protection of the rights of disadvantaged and disadvantaged groups of the population in accordance with the principle of "leaving no one behind" of the UN Sustainable Development Goals , to provide social support and services to persons in need of special protection of the state and society, including persons who are not citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan improve quality;

8) freedom of religion, speech and opinion, access to information, non-discrimination, ensuring gender equality, equal access to quality education and medical services for all, social integration of the elderly, protection of the rights of children, youth, women, persons with disabilities and migrants further improvement of application practices;

9) increase the level of legal, socio-economic and other aspects of support for the family institution, protection of motherhood, fatherhood and childhood, prevention of violence in the family and fight against it;

10) ensuring human economic rights, developing private ownership and public-private partnerships;

11) increase the quality and coverage of education at all levels, develop the continuous education system, ensure the inclusiveness of the education system and its accessibility to all;

12) improving the quality and targeting of information and educational activities in the field of human rights;

13) introduction of innovative principles for the purpose of harmonizing interstate relations, mutual cooperation with international organizations, and quality and timely implementation of recommendations of international treaty bodies on human rights;

14) Implementation of measures aimed at ensuring the election of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the UN Human Rights Council 7 .

Current development stages of the Republic of Uzbekistan a person and is defined by the continuous improvement of the system of ensuring and protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens. During the years of independence, the idea of human rights took a firm place in the minds of citizens, and this is connected with the comprehensive reforms implemented in the country during these years. Our country has chosen its own independent path of renewal and development in the field of domestic and foreign policy. Our country became a member of universal international organizations, as well as leading regional international organizations and actively participated in their activities, among which the UN and its

specialized institutions are the main ones. In addition, Uzbekistan joined the main international documents on human rights. During the period of independence, the main principles in the field of protection of human rights were formed in the policy of Uzbekistan.

Among them, the following can be included:

first, the priority of national interests in the protection of human rights;

secondly, the gradual and step-by-step implementation of democratic reforms

;

thirdly, commitment to the principles of democracy and human rights recognized by its international obligations;

fourth, based on national interests, in the field of human rights

development of international cooperation. 6

Based on these principles, the country is implementing international standards for human rights and freedoms. It should be noted that the main issue of the development of human rights protection systems and mechanisms in Uzbekistan is the effective performance of their duties based on the requirements of international law. To date, the following democratic institutions that ensure and guarantee human rights have been established in Uzbekistan:

1. Constitutional Court;

2. Human rights representative of the Supreme Assembly (Ombudsman);

3. National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

4. Institute of Monitoring of Current Legislation under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

5. Judiciary, prosecutor's office, justice, internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan

6. Children's rights representative (Children's ombudsman)

7. Business ombudsman.

To sum up, in today's era, protection of human rights and freedoms from unlawful aggressions, the implementation of human rights by the states as the fundamental basis of national legislation, the establishment of a clear and functional state policy in the field of human rights, and the formation of a culture of human rights in the minds of young people are truly important. It should be the main goal of the countries that have chosen to build a legal social state. Today, 1.85 billion of the world's population are young people. It can be seen from the above indicators that youth education has a special place in the field of human rights. The young generation that is forming in our society that a person's rights are the highest value. It is necessary to teach and inculcate in their minds the main and main criterion. Because the highest criterion of building an active civil society is to protect the rights and interests of people by law, to shape their social consciousness

and culture. Inculcating such a task in the consciousness of the future generation through education is a vital fact... it is a demand of the times.

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